

The Strategic Issues with Implementing Open Avionics Platforms for Spacecraft¹

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Abstract—Non-aerospace industries from automobiles to consumer electronics are using product platform concepts to accelerate product development. By planning and developing a series of products based on similar architectures, firms can reuse hardware, software, and manufacturing processes to provide a wide range of products, at lower costs and with shorter development cycles. The nature of spacecraft systems creates special technical, strategic, economic, and organizational challenges for implementing product platforms. The low volume, extreme operating environments, long development cycles, short technology cycles, and the nature of government space programs make it difficult for the space industry to benefit from product platform concepts. However, several aerospace organizations are implementing avionics platforms with significant technical, cost, and strategic benefits. This paper discusses the potential strategic benefits of product platform concepts applied to spacecraft avionics.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Despite the low volume and long development cycles of space-flight missions, the commercial concepts of product platforms can be applied to space systems to create value for NASA. This paper identifies this value by applying the management principles and platform practices of the private sector to space systems developed at NASA. Specifically, these theories, principles, and practices are applied to past, present, and future spacecraft avionics applications and the issues and benefits are examined.

1.1 Background

Historically, systems on NASA science missions are developed to meet the requirements of a single mission. Weight, power, and performance were optimized to meet the needs of a single application. The space industry resembled the computer industry of the late 1960s or early 1970s when mainframe computer vendors used closed proprietary architectures, performance was low, volume was low, costs were high, and competition was low with few vendors in the industry. All that changed when IBM introduced the 360/370 with its modular systems [1]. The IBM 360/370 was a broad family of compatible machines with a wide range of performance levels, which was a new concept to the computer industry. More computer firms entered the industry as a result of these modular systems and competition reduced

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price, lower price increased volume, and system performance improved dramatically [1]. Initially, the open architecture permitted more organizations to compete and innovate on the individual modules. IBM, however, realized that open systems reduced their profits and market share, and IBM took several legal and technical steps to close their systems. An anti-trust settlement in the 1970s required them to allow other companies to sell compatible peripherals, but they vigorously attacked other companies that tried to make clones.

The IBM PC is another good example of the benefits of open platform systems on innovation, competition, and cost reduction. Like the IBM 360/370, after IBM introduced the PC, many new firms entered the computer market to produce complementary and competing products and services. The competition grew, performance skyrocketed, and prices dropped.

Implementing modular systems, standard interfaces, and open architectures may produce similar benefits for the space industry. Blindly reusing space systems, however, is not the answer. Failures on the Mars Observer and Galileo Missions are blamed on reusing components from previous missions without completely understanding the requirements of the new missions [2]. Engineers and managers must consider the costs, risks, and benefits of reusing a system and making well-informed decisions. Using standardized interfaces and open architectures will increase performance and system reuse, but they are no substitutes for sound engineering and management practices.

The space industry is changing, and a number of national and international space programs are adopting product platform concepts (see Appendix A). This paper documents the strategic benefits these projects receive by implementing standard interfaces, open architectures, and spacecraft product platforms.

1.2 Objectives

Technical and programmatic issues not related to science objectives often hinder NASA's primary mission "to advance and communicate scientific knowledge and understanding of the Earth, solar system, and the universe." NASA Headquarters periodically issues an Announcement of Opportunity (AO) to select new science missions. NASA would prefer to select a mission based primarily on its scientific merit [3]; however, to ensure mission success, NASA must also consider non-science issues such as the spacecraft, launch vehicle, mission management, and overall costs.

NASA has recently initiated two efforts to simplify the process of developing science missions. In the first

effort, the Rapid Satellite Development Office (RSDO) at NASA maintains a catalog of satellites, including their vendors, capabilities, and fixed costs. Scientists select a spacecraft from the catalog as opposed to developing their own. In another effort, the most recent (Fall 2001) round of Earth System Science Pathfinder (ESSP) science missions will not require scientists to select a launch vehicle. To simplify the process, the winning proposals are provided a launch vehicle. The RSDO and ESSP efforts remove the spacecraft and the launch vehicle as differentiating factors. By providing the satellite and launch vehicle, NASA enables scientists to focus more on scientific issues and less on spacecraft and launch vehicle issues.

Traditionally, NASA sponsored a few large missions (e.g. COBE, Cassini, Galileo, Hubble Space Telescope, etc.), but recently shifted toward smaller, more frequent, less expensive missions. This shift to faster, better, cheaper missions, or FBC, started in the early 1990s with missions like Clementine, NEAR, Mars path-finder (MPF), Lewis/Clark, and others [4]. This shift requires that better systems be developed quickly and cheaply for a wider range of missions. Product variety, quick development, and low cost are all characteristics of product platforms.

In addition to NASA's shifting focus, the ending of the Cold War shifted funding priorities of the Department of Defense (DoD), a historically large funding source of the space industry. The DoD is reducing its spending in aerospace and shifting its focus from custom proprietary systems towards more "off the shelf" open systems [5]. In addition, the reduction in DoD spending forces traditional defense contractors to compete on NASA projects.

1.3 Motivation

Product platforms enable the development of multiple related products that share features, components, subsystems, and processes. Designing a product platform requires the evaluation of current and future requirements in order to develop a core platform to meet those requirements. Platforms allow derivative products to be developed with more variety, shorter schedules, and lower costs.

Appendix A lists projects and organizations that understand the strategic, technical, and economic benefits of product platform concepts and have applied them to their individual missions. Ruffa [6], Strobe [7], Fraeman [8], and others have documented the benefits of modular systems, standard interfaces, and common architectures in reducing costs, accelerating development schedules, and improving system performance to their individual projects.

This paper recognizes the achievements of these individual projects and attempts to define a framework so that other NASA projects, programs, and organizations receive similar benefits. This paper examines strategic concepts popular in academic and business literature, applies these strategic concepts to space systems, and argues that if NASA uniformly adopted these concepts, they would lower the cost and increase the performance of future space missions. In addition, open platform architectures will lower the overall cost of space missions, enabling more frequent science missions to be initiated.

1.4 Specific Objectives

The Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) Program is developing the next generation of weather instruments for the GOES-R mission (the -Rth mission in the -A through -Z series). This paper presents the GOES-R as a case study of applying product platform concepts to a space project. The case study reflects the plans during the formulation phase of the project; however, the project is now (December 2001) in the middle of its preliminary design phase and some of the initial plans may change. The case study is presented at the end of the paper after the strategic benefits of product platform concepts are developed, but the GOES-R Project is briefly introduced here.

The development of the GOES-R instrument started in 2000, proposals were reviewed in early 2001, multiple vendors were awarded study contracts in mid-2001, an instrument vendor will be selected late in 2002, the first launch is in 2012, and there are four launches up to 2022. The GOES-R Project and the instrument vendors are defining and developing an open instrument avionics architecture based on modular systems and standard interfaces. The instrument vendors are encouraged to commercialize and sell components, subsystems, and systems that support the open architecture.

The primary intention of the GOES-R open avionics architecture is to enable upgrades and pre-planned improvements between GOES missions (four missions planned between 2012 to 2022). However, the instrument avionics with its standard interfaces and open architecture, combined with its subsystems and support systems available in a vendor catalog, should enable derivatives of the GOES-R avionics to be used on other space projects, thus lowering the cost of future space missions.

2. STANDARDS, ARCHITECTURES, AND PLATFORMS

NASA creates value when it develops, launches, and operates a scientific satellite. NASA captures science

value when it processes data and expands our scientific knowledge. Aerospace vendors capture monetary value while developing the missions and when they use the knowledge and technology from these missions as a competitive advantage. The following sections examine the strategic benefits of standard interfaces, open architectures, and product platform concepts and how NASA, by implementing these concepts, can gain more value from the systems it develops.

2.1 Standard Interfaces

Standard interfaces are the technical specifications that ensure interoperability between different products or modules. Standard interfaces enable the independent development of modules and complementary products and services (including flight systems, test/validation systems, simulators, etc.).

The following paragraphs summarize network effects and the benefits of standard interfaces for products in a network industry. A network industry is one where the value of a product is based on its compatibility and interoperability with other products. For example, the value of a cell phone is its ability to communicate with other cell phones, and the value of a computer system is its ability to share hardware and software with other computer systems. This paper argues that technology improvements have moved the space industry to a more network 'like' industry. Appendix A lists projects and organizations that implemented product platform concepts and have received the following benefits of a network industry.

2.1.1 Modularity – Modularity is required to capture all of the benefits of standard interfaces. Langlois [9] describes modularity as a general principle for managing complexity. Modules are formed when a complex system is broken-down into discrete pieces that communicate with each other through interfaces within a system architecture. Modularity and standard interfaces are required to implement successful spacecraft avionics platforms that can be quickly configured to meet the requirements of different users.

According to Ulrich and Eppinger [10], modular architectures mean that each functional element of the product is implemented in exactly one physical chunk. This architecture allows the design of one "chunk" to change without impacting other modules. As technology improves and systems get smaller, the mapping of form to function changes and chunks can be merged and functions can be combined. As long as modules reduce complexity and communicate over defined interfaces, they are still modular systems.

An integral system is the opposite of a modular system. Integral systems may have functional elements implemented in more than one “chunk”, and the interfaces between the “chunks” may not be well defined. Integral systems generally offer higher performance than modular systems because their speed, capacity, and other characteristics are optimized and not limited by conforming to predefined interfaces or boundaries.

The benefits and costs of modular systems are important to understand when developing systems. Modularity enables products to be 1) upgraded as technology evolves; 2) added-to by subsystems from other vendors; and 3) adapted to meet other applications [10]. Each of these characteristics of modularity are also critical to implementing product platforms.

Modularity is not free; it can cost a system performance. An integral design can optimize over the entire system, but a modular design optimizes over its “chunk” and communicates to other modules via interfaces. Accommodating for these interfaces can cost power, mass, and performance, but for mature technology, the benefits of modularity exceed the costs [11].

2.1.2 Benefits of Interface Standards – Interface standards are the key to maximizing the benefits of modular systems. Modules with standard interfaces are more easily and reliably developed, tested, and integrated. This is true for both the primary developer and any second source developers. Standard interfaces can be implemented with commercial components, and systems with standard interfaces can be tested with commercial test equipment.

Modules with defined, but non-standard interfaces are dependent on the organization that defined the interface for documentation and potential changes to the interface definition. Documentation, interpretation, and timing errors are greatly reduced with standard interfaces.

Standard interfaces are not free; they can cost a system performance. Standard interfaces often include features for a wide range of applications, and if a design does not need these features, it can cost power, mass, and performance. For example, the MIL-STD-1553B serial data bus is a transformer isolated for added fault tolerance in military applications. Most space applications do not need this feature, and it costs significant mass, power, and volume. However, for many space applications, the benefits of commercially available flight parts and generic test equipment, exceed the costs.

Many of the benefits of standard interfaces are used to gain competitive advantage. As a result, when standards make their products more desirable to users

(compatibility, interoperability, etc.), organizations push for the adoption of standards. When standards enable organizations to operate more efficiently (reduce cost, network effects, etc) in comparison to others, giving them a competitive advantage, organizations push to keep standards or architectures proprietary. The following paragraphs summarize many of the benefits defined by Henderson [12] and Shapiro and Varian [13] and apply these benefits to the space industry.

Network size (many to many) – Product value increases with the number of other individuals who own the same product (e.g. telephones, fax machines, etc.). Computers using standard operating systems and interfaces also create value by letting users exchange software and hardware peripherals. Standards create system compatibility and interoperability, which in turn create more value and more users, and this positive feedback makes the network of users larger. The MIL-STD-1553B command and data bus is a good example of the benefits of network size. Many space organizations support and develop systems for the MIL-STD-1553B bus, and this enables reuse of hardware, software, and procedures.

Complementarities (one to many) – Product value increases with the number of complementary products that are available (e.g., CDs, software, VHS/Beta, etc.). Standards in software, CDs, and videotapes build network effects by enabling people to share complementary products (tapes, etc.) and attracting more users to the network. For space systems these may include cables, hardware, software, test systems, and more. Traditionally, first-tier suppliers provide all complementary products for an avionics system. The standard GOES-R open architecture will enable users to share software, components, subsystems, and test equipment, but it will also provide a market for second-tier suppliers. The MIL-STD-1553B command and data bus is a good example of the benefits of complementarities. The value of this bus is increased by the number of standard space systems (data recorders, transponders, star trackers, etc.) and non-flight systems (test and validation equipment) that are commercially available for this bus.

Learning by using (customer groove-in) – Standard interfaces mean customers invest only once in learning to use the technology (e.g., QWERTY keyboard, Autocad, e-mail). Strobe [7] documented how NASA’s X-Ray Timing Explorer (XTE) Project benefited from having a standard data bus interface (MIL-STD-1773) among systems. Multiple systems were tested with one process and test system which accelerated the testing and integration of the entire spacecraft. The network effect was XTE’s ability to share the software, hardware, and experience gained on one system with another system. Standard interfaces were only one of a number of factors

that contributed to XTE's 15% shorter development schedule and 12% lower development cost.

Modular innovation (plug and play) – Standards enable subsystems or components to be optimized without having to worry about the impact on the overall system. This encourages innovation and improves subsystem performance. Two examples of this are PCs and stereo systems. A modem developer knows the standard interface and not the entire PC, and a CD player manufacturer knows the requirements of the RCA jacks and not the rest of the system. The Essential Services Node (ESN) is a good example of modular innovation. The ESN, shown in Illustration 1, is an application specific integrated circuit (ASIC) and multi-chip module (MCM) that combines many of the integrated circuits (IC) and components necessary to implement the MIL-STD-1553B/-1773 bus into a single chip [14]. The ESN is an innovation that lowers cost, reduces power, simplifies logic, and decreases board space/weight of implementing the standard serial data bus.

Reducing Risk/Uncertainty – Standards also reduce risk and technical uncertainty faced by users. A standard interface enables the use of proven designs and available technology. For instance, one reason VHS became the dominant standard in videotapes was the consumers' uncertainty over the availability of Beta tapes. Both the

NPOES and GOES programs are developing their instruments before the spacecraft and they require instrument vendors to implement interface standards to reduce the uncertainty of instrument to spacecraft compatible issues.

Reducing Lock-in – Lock-in is defined as the situation in which the costs of switching to another product are so high that they effectively prevent any switch from the current product [13]. An example of lock-in may be an electronic mail (e-mail) or word processing program. Regardless of the benefits of the new program, the time (and cost) required to learn a new system, and transfer files locks a user into the current system. Under lock-in, future choices are limited by decisions made in the past. Lock-in can either cause serious problems or be very profitable, depending on your position in the relationship. Open standards reduce users' concern of lock-in. The open standards for CDs and PCs enable users to easily switch CD and PC vendors. Continuing with the MIL-STD-1553B data bus example, multiple vendors support this data bus, which reduces switching costs and eliminates vendor lock-in. The experience of being locked-in to the current GOES instruments vendor's non-standard interfaces and closed architecture, helped gain acceptance of the GOES-R requirement to implement standard interfaces and an open architecture.

Illustration 1 - The ESN, mounted in front of a mirror with its lids removed, combines the features of a circuit card containing a MIL-STD-1553B data system into a single chip – saving cost, power, mass, and volume.

Reducing Price/Costs – Standards shift competition from performance to price when standard interfaces help define the boundaries of products. When features or characteristics become common across products, vendors will start competing for customers based on their price. In addition, standards help reduce the cost to vendors by agreeing on a set of features and then optimizing their manufacturing processes to produce products with these features at a lower cost. The GOES program is not only adopting standard system and subsystem interfaces to reduce cost but also encouraging vendors to commercialize their products to reduce mission costs for other projects.

Shifting Focus – Standards shift focus (or competition) from system to subsystems. When standards enabled stereos to be dis-integrated and components to be sold separately, vendors began competing on performance and the cost of components. As a result, consumers received higher performing products at better prices. In addition, companies began to dis-integrate and started specializing on just one component of the stereo system. This specialization contributes to increased performance and lower prices. With the GOES-R open architecture, multiple vendors can provide subsystems for spacecraft or instrument avionics. The intention is to enable projects to select the systems that meet the performance requirements at the best prices.

Supply-side Economics of Scale – Supply-side economies of scale is defined as the reductions in average and marginal costs that result from the increased size of an operating unit. Dividing the fixed costs over a large number of units achieves economies of scale. This benefit is elusive for space systems since the market is small and volumes are low. However, as the rate of technology improvement continues to slow, system reuse is becoming more practical. In addition, the non-recurring costs (i.e., development costs) of space systems is so high, considerable cost savings are achieved if two or three applications use the same system. The MIL-STD-1553B bus is a good example of a standard bus that has created economies of scale. Components and systems that support the space-qualified bus are commercially available from multiple vendors, which keep their price reasonable compared to custom space systems.

Demand-side Economics of Scale – Demand-side economies of scale is defined as the more something is used, the more it is valued. As a community understands the network effects defined above, the positive feedback continues to increase the benefits, and demand-side economies of scale sustains the standard. In the recent GOES-R interface study, vendors recommended the MIL-STD-1553B as the medium speed data and command bus. Every vendor has experience and designs

that support this bus; so, it has become the de facto standard.

Tipping the Market – Tipping relates to the network effects accelerating the adoption of a technology so that it quickly has market dominance [13]. Tipping depends primarily on two factors: 1) the necessity for variety and 2) the impact of both economies of scale. As Appendix A shows, a number of spacecraft avionics platforms exist, but none of the platform architectures have captured a significant share of the market. The requirement to use an open architecture on multiple instruments and spacecraft may produce the demand-side economies of scale and the commercialization of system that support the open architecture may produce the supply-side economies of scale. The variety requirement to produce tipping is met by the characteristics of product platforms. By meeting both these conditions, the open architecture may 'tip' the market and accelerate the adoption of open platform architectures. Additional benefits of open architectures are discussed next.

The previous paragraphs defined the network effects and the benefits of standard interfaces and the MIL-STD-1553B standard was repeatedly used as an example of how space systems can receive these benefits. This paper argues that if more interface standards were uniformly adopted on space systems, these benefits would be greatly expanded. The GOES-R program is attempting to adopt multiple interface standards uniformly across its program.

2.2 Open Architectures

Open architectures are those where all of the interface information that corresponds to the structure and hierarchy of a system is publicly available. The original IBM PC is an example of an open architecture. Documentation explained the electrical, mechanical, firmware, and software interfaces for the PC's expansion bus. As a result, many new firms and existing firms created systems that supported the PC, increasing the PC's value and performance. Second-tier suppliers developed sound cards, test system cards, data acquisition cards, and many other cards that improved the functionality of the PC. The Macintosh is an example of a closed architecture. The closed architecture prevented complementary products from being developed that could have increased the value of the Macintosh.

Shapiro and Varian [13] describe open systems and strategies as they relate to a firm's competitive strategy. They explain that firms select between openness and control in an effort to maximize their profits. The previous GOES instrument vendor developed a closed architecture and, as a result, the government was locked-

in to this vendor and paid them to make every change to the instrument during the last ten years. As mentioned, this lock-in led to an open architecture for the next generation of GOES instruments.

The space market is not large, and some organizations use closed architectures to maximize their profits and give themselves a competitive advantage. Others do not see the benefits of open systems in a small market, or their new designs are based on closed architectures of past missions. However, if costs were lowered, the volume of missions would increase, and more opportunities would become available.

According to Shapiro and Varian [13], open strategies emerge when no one organization is strong enough to dictate a technology standard or when multiple products must work together (thus making coordination of product design essential). NASA is faced with both conditions, yet currently no industry-accepted open spacecraft avionics architecture has emerged. NASA frequently has multiple products that must work together without the benefit of an open standard. As a result, resources are expended repeatedly to establish interfaces with each different supplier for each different project.

Some space organizations are imitating commercial companies like Microsoft, Cisco, Netscape, and others that keep systems proprietary in order to maintain a competitive advantage [13]. Conversely, organizations new to an industry want openness to neutralize the advantages of established firms. This phenomena was observed in the space industry when the GOES Program interviewed major aerospace vendors (Spring 2000) to collect their comments on the draft requirements for the next generation of GOES instruments. Large vendors that provided complete aerospace systems were reluctant to adopt interface standards and an open architecture; however, smaller vendors that may have lacked the technical or financial capabilities to deliver complete systems were anxious to provide the subsystems that a standard open architecture would enable [15].

Open systems shift profits from the system designer and integrator to the subsystem provider. Apple kept the Macintosh closed and made all the profits. IBM implemented its PC with an open architecture and over time, the profits shifted to the subsystem providers.

In the GOES example, our intention is to help establish an open architecture for spacecraft avionics that will enable more reuse, more second-tier suppliers, higher volumes, and increased performance. This is a difficult task with space systems, but given the list of projects in Appendix A and other examples, we think the space industry may be moving in this direction.

2.2.1 Selecting Standard Interfaces – An architecture is a framework of modules that meet a set of requirements. These modules are connected by a set of interfaces. Interfaces, along with other characteristics including central/distributed, fault-tolerant, level of autonomy, etc., define the system architecture. The critical step in establishing an open architecture is selecting a robust set of standard interfaces. The standard interfaces must thoroughly define the architecture while leaving enough flexibility to support multiple configurations and a pathway for technology upgrades. The standard interfaces selected will determine the performance and longevity of the open architecture.

When competing standards fight for adoption, Shapiro and Varian [13] call these *standards wars*. Standard wars exist in the space industry and are based on interface standards and architecture standards. The definition of a *standards war* is when more than one incompatible technology fights to become the accepted (or de facto) standard. Some commercial examples of standards wars include Beta and VHS, RCA and CBS color TVs, and American and Japanese HDTV. Standards wars are unique to network industries and products that receive some of the benefits of standards described earlier. For example, the benefits of sharing video tapes, CDs, software, tools, telephones and other products are so great that industry and consumers will fight to have one standard adopted. The fighting may include price wars, giving standards or complementary products away, and more.

In some standards wars, only one standard emerges as the winner (VHS over Beta) and in other wars, multiple winners may emerge (PC/DOS and Macintosh over CPM and Commodore). Who wins and the number of winners depend on key assets, strategies, and the market. In aerospace, different open architecture standards may emerge in different segments, but the strategic, technical, and cost benefits will still be significant.

2.2.2 Spacecraft interface standards wars – A standard war is currently (December 2001) underway for the spacecraft's high-speed data bus. MIL-STD-1553B won the standards war for the medium-speed data bus, but at least three data buses are battling for adoption as the high-speed data bus standard – IEEE-1355 (Space Wire), IEEE-1394 (Fire Wire), and ethernet. Different organizations are endorsing different standards, and each organization is developing hardware and software to support their standard. The standard interface that wins this war may effect the GOES-R open architecture, but the GOES-R architecture may also influence the outcome of this standards war.

Summary – There are two types of innovation – autonomous and systemic. Autonomous, or modular,

innovation can be pursued independently from other innovations and systemic innovation requires other complementary innovations and cooperation from others to change the overall system. Modularity, standard interfaces, and open architectures increase autonomous innovation, but may slow or even stop system innovation. Product platforms, as described in the next section, attempt to address these concerns. A major product platform theme, *platforms must be managed as evolving entities* [16], requires product platform developers to consider future changes and encourages systemic innovation.

2.3 Product Platforms

Implementing product platforms is a method for designing multiple related products that share features, components, subsystems, and processes. Designing a product platform requires the evaluation of current and future requirements in order to develop a core platform to meet these requirements. Platforms allow derivative products to be developed with more variety, shorter schedules, and lower costs.

Product platform concepts applied to space systems will produce the benefits of standards and network effects described in the previous sections. Spacecraft avionics vary depending on performance, environment, and mission requirements, but they contain enough common elements to justify implementing product platform concepts. Avionics implemented with standard interfaces, open architectures, and product platform concepts may produce the volume necessary to capture the benefits of network effects while maintaining the flexibility to be configured to meet a wide range of mission requirements.

The development of product platforms can cost from two to ten times more than the development of a simple derivative product [10]. Organizations should develop such a product platform when the potential for derivative products recoups the extra cost of developing a platform. A product platform should be used if either of the following is true: a) technology changes rapidly and b) a product platform would enable vendors to deliver new products quickly to lead users or a new product can be developed with a significant level of subsystem reuse while still providing differentiation.

Appendix A contains a list of national and international projects and organizations that are developing spacecraft based on product platform concepts. Individual projects or programs are benefiting from product platforms with closed architectures, but NASA may not receive the maximum benefit from these platforms. These organizations may be developing closed proprietary architectures to gain competitive advantage, or they may

not perceive a benefit to developing open architecture systems. Regardless, NASA is not capturing the value – described in this paper – that open platforms would provide.

The business and engineering literature contains a number of different methods of developing product platforms. There are three important elements involved in developing product platforms: 1) architectural themes, 2) leveraging strategies; and 3) the implementation process. The technical details of developing spacecraft with product platform concepts are beyond the scope of this paper but are developed in [17] and briefly summarized in the following paragraphs.

2.3.1 Product Platform Architectural Themes – The key to implementing a successful product platform is to design an architecture that can support multiple variations of similar products [16]. The architecture of a product is a combination of subsystems and interfaces. Any product has the potential to develop into a product platform if its architecture is designed to support multiple derivative products. Each subsystem of a product has a specific function and when all the subsystems are combined by the product architecture, the final product has specific form, function, and characteristics. By changing or not including subsystems, derivative products adopt new functions and characteristics.

Architectural themes, principles, and insights determine the success and the life expectancy of a product platform. Meyer and Lehnerd [16], Schulz and Fricke [18], Suh [19], Lyke [20], and Caffrey [21] develop themes that address interfaces, leveraging, management, design, manufacturing, flexibility, and space issues. These themes should be reviewed before implementing a spacecraft product platform.

2.3.2 Product Platform Leveraging Strategies – In the commercial world, a successful product platform can produce a line of profitable products and lead to market dominance. At NASA, a successful product platform can improve performance, decrease development time, and reduce costs across multiple projects, programs, and organizations.

Meyer and Lehnerd [16] define product platform leveraging strategies that explain how products developed for one market segment and performance tier can be leveraged and reused in other markets and tiers. A leveraging strategy defined before a product is developed will insure that the requirements of the other segments are considered in the original design. This will enable products to meet a wider range of customers.

Figure 1 shows several space projects that use product platform concepts. Some space organizations use a

leveraging strategy to move their platform avionics to other market segments and performance tiers. Some of these projects and strategies include the following: multiple projects used the niche strategy; XTE used the horizontal strategy; X2000 and SNAP are using the vertical strategy; and SMEX and IEM used the beachhead strategy.

2.3.3 *Product Platform implementation process* – Academic, business, and technical literature, including Meyer and Lehnerd [16], Roberson and Ulrich [22], Ulrich and Eppinger [10], Schulz and Fricke [18], and Gonzalez-Zugasti, et al. [2], and Simpson, et al. [23], contain examples of defining, optimizing, and implementing product platforms. In addition, in [17] we merge these various processes and introduce a method to define, develop, and implement product platforms for spacecraft avionics.

2.4 *Additional Examples of Product Platforms*

In addition to the spacecraft avionics using products platforms concepts listed in Appendix A and shown in Figure 1, the following paragraphs contain stories about aerospace organizations implementing product platform concepts.

Airbus and Boeing commercial jet airliners – Airbus developed its line of commercial airplanes using product platform concepts and received a significant competitive advantage over Boeing, who prior to the 777 did not use product platform concepts. Boeing optimized the door

design on their commercial airplanes and developed different doors on every airplane and sometimes different doors on the same plane [24]. Airbus used the same doors on each plane and the same door across different models of planes. Therefore, Airbus had one door design, one set of engineering drawings, one parts list, one test plan, one installation process, and one operating procedure. This means that a mechanic could fix, and a flight attendant could operate, any door on an Airbus plane. By not changing the door design, Airbus benefited from the network effects described previously in this paper.

Developing high-performance military airplanes, where it was necessary to optimize every element of the design, formed the Boeing culture. As a result, Boeing planes perform better and achieve better fuel efficacy, but Airbus planes are less expensive to purchase and operate. Traditionally, airplanes required performance optimization, but technology now exceeds requirements and permits vendors to optimize on cost and operations.

The Hughes series of communication satellites – The former CEO of Hughes Space and Communication, Steve Dorfman, revealed during an interview [25] that systems developed for one of Hughes’ class of communication satellites must operate on all three satellites (HS376, HS601, and HS702). It was difficult to get managers and engineers to accept standard platform architecture and give up optimizing their designs, but this method of system development provides a wider range of derivative products to meet the requirements of a wider range of customers.

	Low Earth Orbit (LEO)	Medium Earth Orbit (MEO)	Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO)	High Earth Orbit (HEO)	Deep Space Missions
Best (higher cost & performance, > 3-years)	XTE, TRMM & FUSE (XTE) TIMED (IEM) → EO1 (MIDEX) N/POES, SPOT, GPS.		Boeing HS-Series LORAL L-Series GOES ← TDRS	TRIANA (SMEX-Lite) MAP (MIDEX) ← CONTOR (IEM)	Mars 07, Europa, (X2000) Galileo, Magellan (Galileo)
Better (1 to 3-years)	SAMPEX, SWAS, TRACE, & WIRE (SMEX) → LEOSTAR	FAST(SMEX)		Stereo (IEM)	Deep Impact (X2000)
Good (lower cost & performance, < 1-year)	↑ SNAP-1, PRIMA				

Figure 1 – Several Space Projects implementing product platforms and receiving strategic benefits.

3. THE GOES-R CASE STUDY

The instrument avionics for the next GOES imaging instrument (Advance Baseline Imager, ABI) were not initially defined as a product platform, but in an effort to avoid vendor lock-in, enable subsystems reuse, and support both future upgrades and pre-planned improvements (PPI), many product platform concepts were adopted. NASA is not designing the GOES-R instruments, but rather specifying the requirements, issuing a request for proposal (RFP), reviewing the proposals, awarding multiple study contracts, evaluating the studies, and selecting one of the three vendors for the final development contract. The following paragraphs provide background, define the problem, and specify the requirements for the GOES open architecture.

Background – Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites (GOES) has provided continuous observations of the Earth and its environment since 1968. These satellites are owned and operated by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) manages the design, development, and launch of the spacecraft. The following paragraphs provide background on the GOES Program and NASA’s effort to develop new instruments for the GOES satellites.

Each GOES satellite carries two major instruments: an Imager and a Sounder. These instruments acquire high-resolution visible and infrared data, as well as temperature and moisture profiles of the atmosphere. They continuously transmit data to ground terminals where it is processed for rebroadcast to primary weather services both in the United States and around the world, including the global research community. The instruments on board the satellites measure Earth-emitted and reflected radiation from which atmospheric temperature, winds, moisture, and cloud cover data can be derived.

NOAA and NASA are planning the next generation of GOES instruments – the Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI) and the Advanced Baseline Sounder (ABS). The imaging instrument (ABI) is developed first, followed by the sounder instrument (ABS), and the spacecraft is developed last.

The Problem – Traditionally, instrument avionics systems are developed for a single instrument and a single mission. The GOES-R spacecraft may include five different instruments on four missions. The following are the reasons why the GOES instruments avionics should be based on modular designs, standard interfaces, and open platform architecture:

- 1) The instrument specifications were developed in 2000, the preliminary design started in 2001, the first satellite launch is not until 2012, and at least

four satellites will launch over the next ten years. Decisions made in 2000 will impact missions in 2022. The capability to replace systems and subsystems between flights must exist to incorporate new technology and new requirements.

- 2) The instruments are being developed before the spacecraft and a well-defined interface is critical to a successful instrument/spacecraft integration. In addition, with an open platform, NASA funded technology and subsystems developed for the first instrument, can be reused on other instruments and spacecraft.
- 3) Avionics fit well with the product platform concepts and can be easily leveraged to meet the requirements of other spacecraft market segments. Therefore, the government funding of the GOES open architecture will enable other projects and organizations to benefit from GOES investment in an open product platform.
- 4) The GOES open architecture will be supported by the GOES Program and its vendors for at least twenty years. Other vendors and projects can develop missions, systems, subsystems, components, and support products (cables, simulators, test systems, and non-flight versions) with the knowledge that the architecture and its products will receive long-term support.

The Solution – An outside vendor is developing the GOES imager and therefore the project developed a request for proposal (RFP), a statement of work (SOW), and an instrument requirement document (IRD). In the GOES-R imager instrument RFP, NASA asked vendors to study the benefits of modularity, standards, and open architectures and report the results of their study. The following is the key section from the GOES ABI statement of work (SOW):

The contractor shall perform an interface study and report on the results at the Midterm Review. The contractor shall evaluate the ABI design, performance, risk, cost, and schedule impacts (both non-recurring and recurring) of implementing standard electrical and data interfaces. The contractor shall define an open architecture (i.e., non-proprietary) that supports modularity and pre-planned improvements (PPI). The contractor shall consider the following documents: the common section of the National Polar-orbiting Operational Environmental Satellite System (NPOESS) Sensor Requirements Document (SRD); the draft US Position Paper for the CCSDS standard for Spacecraft On-board Interfaces (SOIF); the draft CCSDS Position Paper on the SOIF Reference Model; and the JPL X2000 interface standard. In addition, the contractor shall evaluate standardizing the following: 1)

data busses (e.g., IEEE-1394, IEEE-1355, MIL-STD-1553B, Low Power IEEE-1553B, Ethernet, I2C, CAN), 2) +28VDC power, 3) UART/RS-422 and ethernet test ports, 4) electronic back-planes (e.g., cPCI), 5) an electronics board size (e.g., 6Ux160), 6) the CCSDS/SOIF proposed reference model, and 7) System Firmware (to support plug-and-play). The contractor shall also propose an instrument/spacecraft command and power architecture. Finally, the contractor should consider and develop as appropriate a commercialization plan that makes ABI components, electronic cards, flight systems, and test systems available in a vendor catalog.

The purpose of this requirement is to have vendors define all subsystem and system interfaces including electrical, mechanical, data, software, and firmware. Three vendors were selected and funded to study the instrument requirements and complete multiple technical studies (including the interface study). Midway through the study period, NASA collected the interface study results, defined a single GOES-R open architecture, and the three vendors will complete the preliminary design of this open architecture with standard interfaces.

Only one vendor is selected to develop the instrument, but the other two vendors will have the knowledge and capability to design systems for GOES-R's open architecture. In fact, the winning vendor could buy subsystems or support systems from the other two vendors if their products better meet the technical or cost requirements. The other two vendors may provide future systems to the open architecture, but more importantly, they have been added to the list of users supporting the open architecture, thus increasing the value of the open architecture to other users through the network effects and positive feedback.

The purpose of the interface study is to encourage vendors to develop modular systems based on standard interfaces and open platform architectures. The following paragraphs analyze the GOES-R study requirements and discuss their implications.

1) *Implement standard electrical and data interfaces* – Vendors often use the same interface from the last project. This may save short-term costs, but future system compatibility, component availability, and multi-vendor integration success requires standard interfaces. Standard interfaces are strategic and will determine the life and changeability of the product platform. In NASA's guidelines on how to implement programs and projects, NPG 7120.5A, NASA recommends to "use technical standards and guidelines with preference given to voluntary consensus standards where practical". Modularity

and interface standards are especially critical in spacecraft systems. Most malfunctions in space systems occur at the interfaces. Proper modularity and standard interfaces will both reduce these errors and determine the level of reuse and longevity of the avionics platform.

- 2) *Define an open architecture (i.e., non-proprietary)* – NASA's plan for projects, NPG 7120.5A, understands the benefits of open systems and requires that "investments in IT shall meet current Agency technical architecture and interoperability standards." This policy translated to spacecraft architectures would receive similar benefits. The architecture for the current GOES instruments is closed and proprietary. This locked NASA into the original vendor and prevented other vendors from supplying components, subsystems, or services.
- 3) *Supports modularity and pre-planned improvements (PPI)* – Modularity simplifies testing and integration and is required to implement an effective product platform concept. In addition, modularity and pre-planned improvements capabilities will enable NASA to replace the current technology when better technology is available. For example, when faster microprocessors or a higher capacity memory chip is available, the replacement is faster and less expensive.
- 4) *Consider the existing interface documents* – Other aerospace projects are either considering or implementing modular designs with standard interfaces. Examining their documentation, learning from their efforts, and using their interface standards may benefit both projects. In addition, the NPOES Project (and the government) spent considerable money evaluating spacecraft interface standards and other projects should benefit from their work. If both the GOES and the NPOES projects adopt the same interface standards, the projects and the vendors could potentially share components, subsystems, test systems, and working experience, thus increasing network effects.
- 5) *Evaluate standardizing the following list of interfaces* – An important element in establishing product platforms is defining the critical interfaces and leaving the other design parameters open to innovation [16]. The SOW listed the critical interfaces and asked the vendors to evaluate standardizing these interfaces. The critical interfaces and their implications are as follows. Data busses: scientific data, command/control, and housekeeping data pass between the instrument and the spacecraft and interface standards are required to enable independent development efforts. Supply voltage: currently, spacecraft and instrument vendors use different supply voltages and this complicates design, testing, and integration and can prevent systems reuse between projects. Test ports: most systems include a test port for software up-

loads and systems testing and a standard test interface would enable cables and test systems to be reused. Electronic back-planes: circuit boards communication via back-planes and a standard back-plane will enable boards to be shared between systems, instruments, and spacecraft. Electronic board size: again, a standard size will enable circuit boards to be shared. Reference model: The internet's OSI reference model enable programs to communicate between dissimilar computer systems and a space-based reference model would provide spacecraft with similar benefits. In addition, the reference model will enable common low-level software on the different systems, supports new microprocessors and data buses with little impact, supports additional future upgrades, and benefits other space missions. System Firmware: A method of self-identifying subsystems and systems to higher level systems is require to support plug-and-play, speed system integration, enable upgrades, and accommodate space-induced component and system degradation (that occurs over time on-orbit). The system firmware concept was not well received by instrument vendors. Integration costs are the highest cost element in developing spacecraft mission. The thought was that standard firmware and plug-and-play features would reduce integration time and save mission development costs, but the volume and technology may not yet justify the concept. Previously in this paper, we examined the benefits and network effects created by the MIL-STD-1553B standard interface. The GOES-R project is attempting to expand these benefits by uniformly adopting multiple interface standards.

- 6) *Propose instrument/spacecraft command and power architecture* – Standard interfaces and modular designs enable subsystem reuse and faster test and integration. The command and power architecture must be defined to permit independent instrument and spacecraft development. In addition, if instruments are going to share systems and subsystems, a power/grounding convention or architecture must be defined. For example, is the system power regulated or unregulated? are the power and chassis grounds common? and where is a star-ground?
- 7) *Develop a commercialization plan and a vendor catalog* – NASA created a catalog of existing spacecraft to reduce mission costs (the RSDO Program), and the GOES Project is encouraging vendors to establish a similar catalog to produce the same results. The GOES Project is asking vendors to develop modular systems based on standard interfaces and open platform architectures. This will allow other vendors to provide future systems, and the vendor competition will lower prices and improve performance. In an overall effort to reduce mission costs and improve system performance, the

project is creating a demand for modular systems with standard interfaces, and at the same time it is creating a supply of those systems. In NASA's guidelines on how to implement programs and projects, NPG 7120.5A, NASA requires all programs and projects to identify commercialization opportunities. During the formulation process, programs and projects are required to develop a Technology and Commercialization Plan. These plans may include program-specific technology, multi-use technology, or new crosscutting technology – both initial opportunities as well as opportunities throughout the project's life cycle. The NPOES program is using the IEEE-1394 as its high-speed data bus, and rather than each instrument vendor developing their own interface card, the program is encouraging one vendor to develop the interface card and sell it to the other vendors. GOES is encouraging its vendors to commercialize common systems so that other GOES vendors can receive similar benefits.

Large vendors in the space industry have traditionally not wanted to sell components or subsystem. They would rather make larger profits by selling complete systems or missions. Recently, however, large vendors are more willing to sell components and subsystems. Some examples of this observation include the following: BAE Systems (formally British Aerospace) and their processors and single board computers (SBC); IIT and their MIL-STD-1394a data bus board; SEAKER and their memory cards and Solid State Recorders (SSR); and others.

The Vendor Proposals – The proposals for the GOES imaging instrument (ABI) were reviewed and three vendors were selected for design study contracts. After the study period, the three vendors will present their preliminary designs and cost data. The government will then select one vendor to complete development of the instrument based on the preliminary design and their cost data. This mini-competition will ensure that the best design at the best cost is selected. The vendor's comments the on standard interfaces are summarized in the following paragraph:

The benefits of modularity, standardization, open architecture, and commercialization include the following: improve system performance; provide an opportunity for component and system reuse; reduce life-cycle cost and schedule risks; enhance the ability to support pre-planned improvements; allow incorporation of third party hardware; minimize the system impact of future technology insertion; and facilitate compatibility with standards spacecraft and low-cost test equipment. The commercial

standards will remain upward compatible during the natural evolution of commercial products. In addition, these concepts could be implemented without impacting the size, mass, or power of the instrument.

Vendors understand and embrace the benefits of modularity, standardization, open architecture, and commercialization. One vendor will be awarded a multi-year contract worth hundreds of millions of dollars to build the instrument. This contract will give them the proper incentives to implement the standard interface and open architecture concepts.

Before the request for proposal (RFP) was released, vendor interviews were held and vendors were asked to comment on the concept of modularity, standard interfaces, open architecture, and a commercialization plan. One vendor said that they were not excited about selling components and subsystems to potential competitors, but that the concept was like the government's small business and minority set-asides programs – they don't like it, but if they were awarded the contract, they would do it.

Summary of the GOES-R Open Architecture – A major argument against modularity, standards, and open architectures in the space industry is that not enough volume exists to benefit from the network effects defined previously in this paper. The GOES-R open architecture is an attempt to address these arguments. By requiring vendors to follow an open architecture, a demand is created for the components, subsystems, and systems that support the open architecture. By encouraging vendors to commercialize and sell components and systems supporting the open architecture, a supply is created.

GOES is a major program that provides the open architecture with strong long-term support. The requirement for multiple vendors to support the open architecture will produce demand-side economies of scale. As more projects use the open architecture supply-side economies of scale will contribute to lower costs. After the network effects are known and positive feedback continues to increase the benefits, demand-side economies of scale will be sustaining. The network effects and the other benefits of an open architecture should surpass the perceived competitive advantages of closed architectures.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper applies strategic principles and platform practices of the private sector to spacecraft avionics development. Specifically, strategic and technical aspects of implementing open architecture spacecraft avionics platforms were examined as pertinent to the

space industry. Based on the analyses in this paper, we conclude that spacecraft avionics based on modularity, standard interfaces, and open platform architectures will create significant value for NASA and other aerospace organizations, despite the low volume and long development cycles of space-flight missions.

The nature of spacecraft systems creates special strategic and technological challenges for the implementation of open platform principles. For example, the project cycle for many space missions is longer than the industry's technology cycle. As a result, improved technology is often available by the time a project is completed, thus thwarting the reuse of components, subsystems, and systems. Low volumes limit the incentive for NASA and the space industry to reuse systems to benefit from economies of scale, economies of scope, and the learning curve. The harsh space environment stipulates that systems must operate over extreme temperature ranges, under vacuum, and exposed to radiation. This necessitates the development of high reliability parts and processes. The combination of the above characteristics, make space systems very expensive. Given high-costs, low-volume, and long development cycles, the competition among vendors and even among NASA organizations is fierce, causing some organizations to shut out rivals by using closed proprietary architectures. Evidence provided in this paper indicates that numerous space organizations are successfully utilized closed platforms to overcome cost, volume, and development cycle issues. Therefore, the goal in this paper is to provide strategic insights for open avionics platforms to be adopted across multiple organizations and for the space industry to receive even greater benefits.

4.1 Significance of Research

Product platforms, through reuse of subsystems and support systems (test, simulation, and other related equipment) enable spacecraft avionics to be developed faster and more reliably, for less cost. Appendix A shows, government and commercial organizations both national and international, adopting avionics platforms based on closed or quasi-open architectures. These organizations may be developing closed architectures to gain competitive advantage, or they may not perceive the benefit of open architecture systems. Regardless, NASA is not capturing the value – described in this paper – that open platforms provide. When each organization develops different platforms with similar functions that are incompatible with each other, NASA is funding redundant efforts. If NASA requires vendors to adopt open architecture based on modular systems with standard interfaces, open platform avionics will emerge as the dominant design. As a result, vendors will stop competing on the superiority of their closed architectures and begin competing on other aspects of space mission

including cost, operations, reliability, data quality, and customer service.

If the added cost of developing closed avionics platforms can be recovered in as little as two missions, NASA will gain significant benefit if open avionics platforms are adopted across organizations and companies. This is not to suggest that a single open architecture will emerge as the dominant design for spacecraft avionics. Multiple open architecture platforms may emerge, where different platforms serve a particular market segment or performance niche. Finally, an avionics dominant design will shift engineering focus and design innovation to other aspects of space missions and other dominant designs, and their benefits, will emerge as well.

4.2 Limitations and Advantages

This paper applies academic and business concepts from network industries to the space industry, but there are significant differences between the two industries. In the space industry, volume is low, development cycles are long, costs are high, product variety is great, and only a few customers exist. The space industry, however, is changing – costs are dropping, performance is exceeding demand, modular systems are replacing integral systems, horizontal organizations are replacing vertical organizations, and more frequent but smaller space missions are being initiated. If the space industry continues to transition to a more network ‘like’ industry, organizations that adopt the academic and business concepts discussed in this paper may gain significant strategic, technical, and competitive advantage over other organizations.

4.3 Recommendations for Further Work

There are at least three very relevant topics related to spacecraft avionics that should be examined to complete

the process of studying the implementation of open spacecraft avionics.

Organizational Issues – There are four main areas of study related to product platform development: strategy, technical, economic, and organizational. Organizational issues, however, are probably the most important when implementing a new initiative. These issues must be studied and solutions found if organizations are to receive the full benefit of applying product platform concepts to spacecraft avionics.

Software – This paper concentrates on the strategic benefits of hardware platforms. Software is an equally important strategic, economic, and technical issue for spacecraft avionics that requires additional study.

Plug-and-Play and Product Architectures – Plug-and-play is often a misused phrase and a misunderstood concept. Modular systems, standard interfaces, open architectures, and product platforms are all elements of plug-and-play, but the defining characteristic of plug-and-play is the ability of a device to identify itself to the host system. The host system determines how to communicate with the target device based on the information the host reads from the target device. The information read may be stored in hardware, software, or firmware and may include an address, device characteristics, or device drivers. Plug-and-play devices must include modular systems, standard interfaces, and open architectures, but they should also be hardware (microprocessor) and software (operating system) independent. Space systems are not replaced as frequently as PCMCIA cards, but the cost of spacecraft test and integration is higher than hardware costs, and a small increase in hardware design costs may yield a significant cost savings in the spacecraft integration. There are a number of standards available (IEEE-1275 and more), but additional work is required to determine which standard is best for space applications.

APPENDIX A – SPACECRAFT PROJECTS IMPLEMENTING PLATFORM CONCEPTS

Date	Project	Comments	Reference
April 1993	SGOAA Standard / NASA/JSC	The Space Generic Open Avionics Architecture (SGOAA) Adopted as a SAE standard (SAE AS-4893) Generic Open Architecture (GOA) Framework.	Wray, R. [26]
August 1995	GOA / SAE		
1995	IEEE P896.1 working group Futurebus+	The IEEE P896.1 working group designed an open architecture space-flight computer bus that is commercially supported, high performance, low power, and meets the robust space requirements.	Marshal [27]
1995	Iridium Motorola & partners	All 66 spacecraft in the network and their systems were designed as modules to be assembled onto the satellite in only 22-days.	Aviation Week [28]
1996	ASAA Project USAF, Air Force Research Lab	This papers presents an Air Force approach to defining an Advanced Spacecraft Avionics Architecture (ASAA) which embodies commercial standards and modern system design principles.	Borky, J. [29]
1996	XTE Project NASA/GSFC XTE, TIMED, and FUSE Missions	The X-Ray Timing Explorer (XTE) Project implemented many product platform concepts and saved 12% on its budget and 15% on its schedule. But the significant cost savings were the 45% savings in the system level costs.	Strope, D. [7]
1997	IEM Architecture JHU/APL TIMED, CONTOUR, and Stereo Missions	APL is using a beachhead product platform strategy to leverage their initial version of the IEM to other missions. The IEM architecture is used on three missions including one low Earth orbit (LEO) and two high Earth orbit (HEO).	Fraeman, M. [8]
1998	MIDEX Architecture NASA/GSFC MAP and EO1 Missions	The scaleable, distributed, modular, and fault-tolerant architecture with standardized interfaces used on multiple missions	Ruffa, J. [6]
1998	SMEX-Lite, NASA/GSFC TRIANA	The architecture is distributed, modular, independent, and integratable. Addressed many of the changeability, standardization, and openness principles needed to implement the open avionics platform.	Watzin, J. [30]
1998	Platform for Interplanetary Mission, NASA/JPL	A method for designing product platforms for an interplanetary spacecraft platform. The model is used to identify possible subsystems of each spacecraft that could be made common to other missions and the impact of architecture decisions on the performance of the product.	Gonzalez-Zugasti, [2]
2000	X2000 NASA/JPL Europa Mission	The X2000 Project is developing a multi mission avionics system architecture based on two commercial bus standards, the Philips I ² C bus and the high-speed IEEE-1394 bus.	Chau, S. [31]
2000	PRIMA Alenia Aerospazio Italy	The Italian Space Agency is developing a small spacecraft platform with a common core that minimizes resources and enables subsystem reuse on multiple missions.	Galeazzi, C. [32]
2000	PROTEUS Saab/Ericsson Sweden	PROTEUS capitalizes in technology advances to develop an open architecture avionics platform.	Hult, T. [33]
2000	LEOSTAR Matra Marconi Space, France	LEOSTAR is a platform of multi-mission spacecraft that includes a generic avionics core, configured to meet many different mission requirements.	Durteste, C. [34]
2000	SNAP Surry Satellite England	Surry capitalized on the 10-years of success developing micro-satellites and expanded into developing nano-satellites.	Wahl, Z. [35]
2000	NPOES USAF, NASA, & NOAA	The National Polar-orbiting Operational Environmental Satellite System (NPOES) Program is developing multiple instruments before the spacecraft and is requiring vendors to use standard instrument interfaces.	NPOSE Interface Req. Document [36]
2001	GOES/ABI, NASA/GSFC	The GOES Project, to develop the next generation weather instruments, is studying modularity and standard interfaces, and will define an open architecture.	GOES/ABI SOW [37]

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6. BIOGRAPHIES

Mr. Robert Caffrey is an Instrument Manager at NASA GSFC and has worked on instruments to monitor weather, oceans, pollution, ozone, and volcanos. He has been at GSFC since September 1985 and spent the first eight years developing both flight hardware and software for the Shuttle Solar Backscatter Ultraviolet (SSBUV) instrument and payload.

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